

ECONOMY

Overcoming the middle-income trap through transformative power.

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(DTTC) - Vietnam can only overcome the middle-income trap when it develops sufficiently strong transformative capacity, allowing for a synchronized change in its development model.

Vietnam is at a pivotal moment in its development process. After decades of maintaining high growth rates, the economy has accumulated enough strength and momentum to emerge from poverty and rise to the middle-income group.

However, it is at this point that familiar growth drivers are gradually weakening, while new drivers have yet to fully emerge. This reality raises the question: Will Vietnam continue to move forward by old inertia, or will it have the capacity to enter a new, transformative phase of development?

The core issue is not whether there is growth, but whether that growth is strong enough to create a breakthrough or merely keeps the economy at a high-average level. International experience shows that many countries that experienced strong growth for extended periods saw their growth stagnate and become prolonged once their initial advantages wore off.

Therefore, the middle-income trap is not an unusual phenomenon, but rather a common outcome of a development model that has reached its limits.

Over the years, Vietnam has effectively leveraged traditional growth drivers such as its abundant labor force, competitive costs, open trade, and strong attraction of foreign investment. As a result, the economy has grown rapidly in size, incomes have improved, and macroeconomic stability has been maintained.

However, it is worth noting that the growth model heavily reliant on expanding inputs and participating in low value-added stages is becoming increasingly difficult to sustain, as global competition intensifies, technology changes more rapidly, and cost advantages gradually diminish.

At the current stage of development, the crucial question is how to transform the development model towards greater depth. If growth is considered an end in itself, it will quickly reach its limits. Only when growth is seen as the result of profound changes in institutions, economic structure, and national capacity can the economy achieve more sustainable long-term development.

In practice, institutional reforms in Vietnam have achieved many important results, particularly in maintaining stability, improving the investment environment, and enhancing macroeconomic management capacity. However, these reforms still bear the imprint of a managerial mindset rather than a constructive one. Policies remain fragmented by sector and level, lacking sufficiently strong coordination mechanisms to formulate systematic long-term development priorities. In the new context, institutions not only need to be "open" but also capable of guiding, coordinating, and leading the process of upgrading the economy. Economically, Vietnam has industrialized rapidly, but primarily based on low value-added sectors and heavily reliant on foreign investment. This has boosted exports and created jobs, but has not automatically translated into high productivity and endogenous competitiveness.

Without a clear upgrading strategy, the economy can easily fall into a state of "growth without breakthrough," where the scale continues to expand but the quality of development does not improve proportionally.

The key point, and also the biggest challenge, lies in national capacity. Vietnam has received many resources from outside, from capital and technology to institutional experience. However, the ability to internalize these resources remains limited. Learning has not been systematically organized, policy coordination has been inconsistent, and long-term strategic planning capacity remains a weakness. It is national capacity that ultimately determines the ability to successfully transition to a higher development trajectory.

History shows that no miracle is created from a single policy or a short-term growth period. Breakthroughs in development, if they occur, are always the result of a synchronized and sustained transformation process. The core of this process lies in three closely related pillars.

First and foremost, institutions must create long-term, stable, and reliable signals so that economic actors have a basis for investment, innovation, and risk-taking in the long term. Without these signals, growth is likely to be short-term and dependent on temporary advantages.

Next, the economic structure needs to be deliberately upgraded, shifting from expansion to improving productivity, quality, and added value. This is a prerequisite for growth that is not only rapid but also sustainable and has the potential to spread.

Ultimately, national capacity must be strong enough to organize the learning process, coordinate policies, and adapt promptly to domestic and international changes. Without this capacity, reforms are likely to become fragmented and ineffective.

Only when these three pillars are implemented simultaneously and support each other can positive development cycles be formed: institutions guiding long-term investment; investment driving economic upgrading; and the upgrading process contributing to the accumulation of national capacity and strengthening institutions at a higher level.

When these cycles become strong enough, the economy can overcome the limitations of the old model and enter a self-sustaining growth trajectory, where growth becomes an inevitable outcome, not a short-term goal.

Without creating the necessary transformation to form positive growth cycles, overcoming the middle-income trap and achieving a growth breakthrough will be very difficult.

Therefore, the choice is to proactively move into a deeper phase of reform, viewing development as a deliberate transformation process that requires perseverance, effective coordination, and a long-term vision.

The biggest challenge in the coming period lies not in resources, but in the capacity for transformation. If Vietnam can overcome this threshold, it will have the opportunity to enter a new development trajectory, in which growth is not only faster in speed, but also deeper in quality and more sustainable in foundation.

Conversely, if sufficiently significant changes are not made, the risk of remaining stuck in a state of "medium stability" will become increasingly apparent.

Resources are no longer the biggest obstacle; the real challenge lies in the capacity for transformation. The decisive moment has arrived, and the answer depends on whether Vietnam dares to seize the opportunity and act.

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